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JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENCE NETWORKS

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The Journal of International science networks

Computer Networks is an international, archival journal providing a publication vehicle for complete coverage of all topics of interest to those involved in the **computer communications networking** area. The audience includes researchers, managers and operators of networks as well as designers and implementors. The Editorial board will consider any material for publication that is of interest to those groups.

SUBJECT COVERAGE

The topics covered by the journal but not limited to these are:

1. Communication Network Architectures:

New design contributions on Local Area Networks (LANs), Metropolitan Area Networks (MANs), Wide Area Networks (WANs) including Wired, Wireless, Mobile, Cellular, Sensor, Optical, IP, ATM, and other related network technologies, as well as new switching technologies and the integration of various networking paradigms.

2. Communication Network Protocols:

New design contributions on all protocol layers except the Physical Layer, considering all types of networks mentioned above and their performance evaluation; novel protocols, methods and algorithms related to, e.g., medium access control, error control, routing, resource discovery, multicasting, congestion and flow control, scheduling, multimedia quality of service, as well as protocol specification, testing and verification.

3. Network Services and Applications:

Web, Web caching, Web performance, Middleware and operating system support for all types of networking, electronic commerce, quality of service, new adaptive applications, and multimedia services.

4. Network Security and Privacy:

Security protocols, authentication, denial of service, anonymity, smartcards, intrusion detection, key management, viruses and other malicious codes, information flow, data integrity, mobile code and agent security.

5. Network Operation and Management:

Including network pricing, network system software, quality of service, signaling protocols, mobility management, power management and power control algorithms, network planning, network dimensioning, network reliability, network performance measurements, network modeling and analysis, and overall system management.

6. Discrete Algorithms and Discrete Modeling

Algorithmic and discrete aspects in the context of computer networking as well as mobile and wireless computing and communications. Fostering cooperation among practitioners and theoreticians in this field.

TYPES OF CONTRIBUTIONS CONSIDERED

The primary purpose of the journal is to publish original and complete papers covering a specific topic or project in the above mentioned areas in sufficient detail and depth to be of practical use to interested readers. The readers should benefit from the novel solutions and analyses presented in the papers. Enhanced, extended versions of quality papers presented at conferences or workshops can be submitted to our journal for review. Note that papers which were already published with the same contents or simultaneous submission of the same paper to other journals or conferences will not be considered for publication in our journal and will be immediately rejected.

Dataset Articles. Computer Networks also publishes *micro-articles* that describe *open datasets* available in a redacted and organized way. The purpose is for researchers to easily share and reuse each other's datasets by publishing data articles that:

- (i) Describe collected data in detail, facilitating reproducibility of experiments and improvements over proposed techniques, thus promoting rigorous experimentation and data analysis.
- (ii) Describe tools developed to collect, analyze, and visualize data.

Open-Source Software Articles. Computer Networks additionally publishes *micro-articles* that describe open source software that has been used to obtain scholarly results in the area of computer networks.

OBJEKTNI TANIB OLIH TIZIMLARINING ANIQLASH USULLARI

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Annotatsiya: Obyektni tanib olish texnologiyalari turli usullarga asoslanadi va ularning samaradorligi tasvirning aniqligi, shovqin darajasi, obyektning murakkabligi va o'qitilgan modelning sifati kabi omillarga bog'liq. Obyektlarni tanib olishning yanada aniqroq usullari optical character recognition sodda tushintirganda rasmni ichidan belgilarni tanib olish tizimi

Kalit so'zlar: Obyektni aniqlash (Object Detection), Kompyuter ko'rishi (Computer Vision), OCR (optical character recognition), FlexiCapture.

Belgilarni optik tanib olish (ingl. optical character recognition, OCR) - bu qo'lda yozilgan, yozilgan yoki bosilgan matn tasvirini matnli ma'lumotlarga mexanik yoki elektron tarjima qilib kompyuterda (masalan, matn muharririda) belgilarni namoyish qilish uchun ishlatiladigan tizim. Sodda tushintirganda rasmni ichidan belgilarni tanib olish tizimi.[1] E'tirof kitoblar va hujjatlarni elektron shaklga o'tkazish, xo'jalik hisobi tizimlarini avtomatlashtirish yoki veb-sahifada matnlarni nashr etish uchun keng qo'llaniladi. Belgilarni optik jihatdan tanib olish sizga matnni tahrirlash, so'zlar yoki iboralarni qidirish, ixcham shaklda saqlash, materialni sifatini yo'qotmasdan namoyish etish yoki bosib chiqarish, ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish va matnga elektron tarjima, formatlash yoki konversiyani qo'llash imkonini beradi. Matnni optik tanib olish - bu obyektning tanib olish, sun'iy intellekt va kompyuterli ko'rish sohasidagi tadqiqot muammosi. Optik belgilarni aniqlash (OCR) tizimlari ma'lum bir shrift bilan ishlash uchun kalibrlashni talab qiladi; oldingi versiyalarda dasturlash uchun har bir belgining tasviri kerak edi; dastur bir vaqtning o'zida faqat bitta shrift bilan ishlashi mumkin edi. Hozirgi vaqtda eng keng tarqalgan bo'lib, ko'pgina shriftlarni yuqori aniqlik bilan tan oladigan "aqlli" tizimlar. Ba'zi OCR tizimlari rasmlarni, ustunlarni va boshqa matnli bo'lmagan qismlarni o'z ichiga olgan matnning asl formatini tiklashga qodir(1-rasm).

1-rasm. OCR tizimi. Rasmdan belgini aniqlash.

OCR tarixiga nazar soladigan bo'lsak 1929 yilda Gustav Tauschek Germaniyada OCR usuli uchun patent oldi, undan keyin Pol V. Xandel 1933 yilda AQShda o'z uslubiga patent oldi. 1935 yilda Tauschek ham uning usuli uchun AQSh patentini oldi. Tauschek mashinasi shablonlar va foto detektoridan foydalanadigan mexanik qurilma edi va yangi tarixi 1993 yilda Rossiyaning ABBYY kompaniyasining matnni tanib olish texnologiyasi chiqarildi. Uning asosida ommaviy foydalanuvchilar uchun bir qator korporativ echimlar va dasturlar yaratilgan. Xususan, ABBYY FineReader matnni aniqlash dasturi, mobil qurilmalardan matnni tanib olish uchun dasturlar va ABBYY FlexiCapture oqim hujjati va ma'lumotlarni kiritish tizimi. ABBYY OCR matnni tanib olish texnologiyalari litsenziyalari Fujitsu, Panasonic, Xerox, Samsung, EMC va boshqalar kabi xalqaro IT kompaniyalardir [1].

Qog'ozdagi matnda lotin belgilarini aniq tanib olish hozirda faqat skanerlangan bosilgan hujjatlar kabi aniq tasvirlar mavjud bo'lganda mumkin. Muammoning ushbu formulasi bilan aniqlik 99% dan oshadi, mutlaq aniqlikka faqat odam tomonidan keyinchalik tahrir qilish orqali erishish mumkin. Qo'lda yozilgan "bosma" va qo'lda yozilgan standart matnlarni, shuningdek boshqa formatdagi bosma matnlarni (ayniqsa juda ko'p sonli belgilarga ega) tanib olish muammolari hozirgi kunda faol tadqiqot mavzusidir. Usullarning aniqligini bir necha usul bilan o'lchash mumkin va shuning uchun ular juda katta farq qilishi mumkin. Masalan, tegishli dasturiy ta'minot uchun ishlatilmaydigan ixtisoslashgan so'zga duch kelinsa, mavjud bo'lmagan so'zlarni qidirishda xato ko'payishi mumkin. Belgilarni onlayn tanib olish, ba'zida optik belgilarni aniqlash bilan aralashtiriladi. Ikkinchisi matnni tasvirlashning statik shakli bilan ishlaydigan oflayn usul bo'lib, onlayn belgilarni tanib olish yozuv paytida harakatlarni hisobga oladi. Masalan, PenPoint OS yoki planshet kompyuter yordamida onlayn tan olishda siz chiziq o'ngdan chapga yoki chapdan o'ngga yozilganligini aniqlashingiz mumkin. Yana bir keng o'rganilgan muammo - bu qo'l yozuvini tanib olish. Ayni paytda erishilgan aniqlik qo'lda yozilgan "bosilgan" matndan ham past. Yuqori natijalarga faqat kontekstli va grammatik ma'lumotlar yordamida erishish mumkin. Masalan, tanib olish jarayonida lug'atda butun so'zlarni izlash matndagi individual belgilarni aniqlashga qaraganda osonroq. Tilning grammatikasini bilish, shuningdek, so'zning fe'l yoki ism ekanligini aniqlashga yordam beradi. Ayrim qo'lda yozilgan belgilar shakllari ba'zida qo'lda yozilgan matnni aniq tanib olish uchun (98% dan ortiq) ma'lumotga ega bo'lmisligi mumkin.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar.

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